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Organizational justice moderate: The effect of leader-member exchange on work engagement and impact on organizational citizenship behavior

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to analyze the role of organizational justice in moderating the influence of leader-member exchange on work engagement and its impact on organizational citizenship behavior (Study of the Regional III National Road Implementation Work Unit, Bali Province). The population of this research is all employees who work in the Bali Province Region III National Road Implementation Work Unit, totaling 87 employees using non-probability sampling with a saturated sample method, so the sample used was 87 employees. The data collection method was carried out by survey through questionnaires and interviews for pre-survey. The data analysis method used in this research is SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) based on Partial Least Square (PLS). The research results show that leader-member exchange and work engagement have a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. Work engagement partially mediates and complements the influence of leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational justice quasi-moderates the influence of leader-member exchange on work engagement. The implication of this research is that to improve employee organizational citizenship behavior, it is necessary to increase leader-member exchange, work engagement, and organizational justice by conducting competency and skills training for superiors, building a positive and enjoyable work environment to increase work concentration, listening to the aspirations of employees. regarding existing complaints and reviewing existing regulations within the agency in order to increase employee satisfaction and fairness.

Keywords: Leader-Member Exchange; Work Engagement; Organizational Justice; Organizational Citizenship Behavior

1. Introduction

OCB behavior that is less than optimal tends to reduce the company's image and has a negative impact if employees do not have good OCB behavior. One factor that can influence OCB is leader-member exchange. Leader-member exchange (LMX) is said to be one of the important roles that can create OCB behavior. LMX is the key to success in an organization because treatment from superiors can create a quality relationship that occurs which can change employee behavior for the better (Setyati & Utari, 2023). LMX is based on social exchange theory which provides a basis for viewing the nature of employee work relationships with superiors (Garg & Dhar, 2017).

LMX shows how the quality of the relationship between superiors and subordinates, the quality of these relationships depends on the development of reciprocal respect, trust, loyalty, and a sense of obligation between both parties, good quality LMX increases employee satisfaction and gives rise to favorable work outcomes such as OCB (Teng et al., 2020). Good quality relationships can increase business efficiency, where leaders build different relationships with each employee. (Nugroho et al., 2020). High quality LMX relationships enable strong and productive communication between work teams, and employees with high LMX quality will show more of their effort at work (Zhang et al., 2020).

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The quality of good interaction and exchange relationships between superiors and subordinates has a beneficial influence that motivates employees to carry out OCB (El, 2019). Research by Zhang et al. (2020) and Meilane et al. (2023) shows that LMX has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Sheeraz et al. (2020) stated that high quality LMX has a significant positive value with OCB because a superior can influence how his employees behave with a reciprocal relationship, employees who have a good quality relationship with their superiors will feel they have an obligation to reciprocate this treatment by behaving more positively such as OCB. to the company. LMX has an influence in increasing employee OCB, good LMX quality increases employee behavior in showing profitable roles without formal recognition from the organization (Santoso et al., 2022). High-quality relationships between superiors and subordinates can positively increase the influence on employees in carrying out OCB (Kapil & Rastogi, 2020). LMX has an important element in improving the relationship between superiors and subordinates which motivates employees to carry out OCB (Heriyadi et al., 2020).

Apart from LMX, work engagement is also an important factor in increasing OCB (Prabowo et al., 2019). Employee work engagement is very important in increasing OCB because a high level of engagement makes employees more active at work and will consider their work important so that it will make them serious in doing their work which will then encourage them to show positive behavior in an initiative manner to contribute to success. organization (Attalia et al., 2022). Work engagement is a positive psychological condition in which individuals feel completely bound and connected to their work, this includes feelings of deep attachment, full concentration, and a high sense of enthusiasm and energy towards work tasks (Xiong & Wen, 2020). Work engagement is a strong and positive form of motivation that can influence individual performance and well-being at work (Chan, 2019). Rahman & Karim Research (2022); Farid et al. (2019) shows that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Mahmudi & Elmi (2020) show that work engagement has a significant positive effect on OCB because employees who have high engagement will be more enthusiastic about contributing to achieving organizational success with positive behavior in completing tasks outside of work.

Work engagement is important in building closeness in an organization. Organizational members have a work dependency which causes the importance of work engagement to be increased. The social exchange theory in this research is relevant in explaining how someone feels connected to their work. This is because social exchange theory explains that when good LMX qualities are possessed by subordinates, where superiors tend to be more comfortable working with subordinates who have good work enthusiasm, work performance and intelligence, employees will feel that they need to reciprocate this relationship with positive treatment, work engagement. includes high levels of energy and enthusiasm for work (Teng et al., 2020). Engaged individuals feel energized and motivated to complete their tasks because work engagement involves feelings of deep and significant attachment to work so that individuals feel that their work has important meaning and value (Arumdani & Sopiah, 2022).

Research by Purwanto et al. (2021) stated that LMX does not have a significant influence on OCB. This research is in contrast to research from Meilane et al. (2023) and Santoso et al. (2022) where it is said that LMX influences OCB significantly because the higher the quality of the relationship you have, the more positive influence employees will have in carrying out OCB. Other research conducted by Mahmudi & Elmi (2020) shows that LMX can influence OCB positively and significantly.

Based on the inconsistencies in the results of previous research on the influence of LMX on OCB, this influence does not appear clear. This condition makes it important to add a mediating variable to the influence of LMX on OCB so that this influence can be explained in more depth. Mediation is a process in which an intermediary variable explains the relationship between two other variables (Xiong & Wen, 2020). Work engagement acts as an intermediary variable that explains how the relationship between LMX and OCB is formed. Individuals who have high levels of work engagement tend to be more motivated to make contributions outside of official work duties, they may be more likely to participate in OCB, such as helping coworkers, sharing knowledge, or contributing to organizational initiatives (Peprah, 2020). Work engagement as an intermediary, the relationship between LMX and OCB becomes more structured and explainable. Through this mechanism, organizations can better understand how the quality of relationships between leaders and team members can influence positive employee behavior in the workplace.

The quality of LMX relationships has an influence on the behavior of followers and how much employees can be engaged in their work so that they can provide positive organizational citizenship behavior that contributes to the company (Liu, 2023). Research by Sheeraz et al. (2020) stated that work engagement can partially and positively mediate the influence of LMX on OCB. When employees have a good quality two-way interaction relationship with their superiors, it tends to make them more attached to their work, making employees view the organization more positively and developing OCB. . Research by Edward & Sulastri (2020); Andrew & Sopian (2012) stated that the mediating role of work engagement on the influence of LMX on OCB is positive and significant.

Good quality LMX relationships, especially with an in-group that gets more attention and support from the leader, can give team members a sense of recognition and appreciation. This can increase the level of work engagement because team members feel important and appreciated by their leader (Lai et al., 2020). Although several research results conducted by Kapil & Rastogi (2020) and Lai et al. (2020) explained that there is a relationship between LMX and work engagement, but the direction of this relationship is indicated to change according to the conditions of the third variable. In this research, the influence of LMX on work engagement will be moderated by organizational justice. Moderating variables can change the strength or direction of the relationship between the independent variable (cause) and the dependent variable (outcome).

Organizational justice refers to employees' perceptions of the extent to which organizational policies, procedures and decisions are implemented fairly and objectively (Park et al., 2022). Organizational justice can strengthen or weaken the quality of relationships between leaders and team members. If team members feel that the organization applies fairness in policies, procedures, and decisions, this can influence LMX and engagement in their work. This is supported by research conducted by Montañez-Juan et al. (2019) which explains that organizational justice can be a moderating variable on the influence of work on job satisfaction. Other research conducted by Peprah (2020) shows that organizational justice variables can strengthen or moderate the influence of employee perceptions on employee engagement. Sarti (2019) in his research stated that the resulting moderating role is significant, where a sense of justice can influence the quality of LMX relationships that occur and influence employees' sense of engagement with their work.

Work engagement can influence OCB, where when employees have a sense of justice it influences them to be actively engaged and enthusiastic in doing work, this attachment makes them provide positive behavior to the company to build and improve the organization (Aggarwal & Mittal, 2021). Research by Hasyim & Palupiningdyah (2021) states that when employees feel they are treated fairly and well cared for by the company, they tend to have a good quality close relationship with their leaders so they will be more attached to their work and organization which will make them put in extra effort. to repay the organization by engaging in OCB. Previous research results have described the moderating role of organizational justice, but there is still very limited research regarding the moderating role of organizational justice on the influence of LMX on work engagement, so this research is deemed important to carry out.

2. Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Lee (2020) states that LMX significantly influences the OCB behavior of employees within the company, a person tends to provide a "good citizen" attitude when they have a good quality relationship with their superior because this two-way relationship develops a sense of trust which can stimulate positive employee behavior. LMX reflects the extent to which leaders and members understand each other, trust each other, and support each other. The better the quality of these relationships, the more likely members are to exhibit OCB behavior. LMX has a significant positive influence on OCB because when employees have a good quality relationship with their superiors they will feel given more support, development opportunities and feel guided by their superiors, this makes employees tend to reciprocate treatment with OCB behavior carried out with a high level of voluntary behavior. to the company (Zhang et al., 2020). The results of research conducted by Kapil & Rastogi (2020) show that LMX can cause an increase in OCB. Research conducted by Sa'adah & Rijanti (2022) shows that LMX has a positive effect on OCB because leaders play an important role in the organization. Results of other research conducted by Wicaksono & Priyono (2022); Santoso et al. (2022) and Meilane et al. (2023) shows that there is a positive and significant effect of LMX on OCB.

2.1. H1: Leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior.

Leaders who have good quality relationships with subordinates have the potential to influence and motivate employee attitudes in a positive direction, which in particular causes employee work engagement to increase due to the good relationship between superiors and subordinates (Rahman & Karim, 2022). High LMX quality means employees receive a lot of support from their superiors and there is open communication from superiors and subordinates, thus increasing employee engagement in doing their work (Dewi et al., 2019). High LMX quality is positively related to work engagement, this makes employees more engaged in work so that employees tend to perform better and reduces employees' intention to leave the organization (Utami & Zakiy, 2020). The results of research conducted by Lai et al., (2020); Kurniawan & Ranihusna (2019); Priwisata & Purba (2019); Mulligan et al. (2021) shows that LMX has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. The results of research conducted by Kapil & Rastogi (2020) show that the quality of LMX relationships between superiors and subordinates can cause work engagement to also increase. Based on the previous description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

2.2. H2: Leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on work engagement

Research by Farid et al. (2019) shows that employees who show high engagement in their work tend to be more likely to do more work outside of formal duties and show behavior that benefits the company. Research by Mahmudi & Elmi (2020) shows that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on OCB because employees who have high engagement will be more enthusiastic about contributing to achieving organizational success with positive behavior in completing tasks outside of work. Hasyim & Palupiningdyah (2021) stated that when employees feel they are more attached to work and the organization, it will make them exert extra effort to repay the organization by engaging in OCB. Park Research (2019); Kundi & Manipal (2023); Rahman & Karim (2022); Rekha & Sasmita (2019); Urbini et al. (2020); and Lee-Peng et al. (2019) stated that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on OCB. Based on the previous description, the following hypothesis is proposed:

2.3. H3: Work engagement has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior

Work engagement can act as a mediator in the relationship between leader-member exchange (LMX) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Work engagement can act as a mediator between the quality of the relationship between leaders and team members and the level of OCB. Research by Sheeraz et al. (2020) stated that work engagement can partially and significantly mediate the influence of LMX on OCB, where employees who have a good quality two-way interaction relationship with their superiors tend to be more attached to their work, making employees view the organization more positively and develop OCB.

Research by Mahmudi & Elmi (2020) shows that good quality exchange relationships between superiors and subordinates make employees engaged in doing their work because employees will feel more cared for. When employees are engaged, employees will feel emotionally attached to the company which will give rise to positive behavior in the form of OCB to help achieve company goals. Research by Edward & Sulastris (2020) shows that the mediating role of work engagement in the influence of LMX on OCB is significant. Andrew & Sopian (2012) stated that work engagement can positively and significantly mediate the influence of LMX on OCB. The results of research conducted by Xiong & Wen (2020); Aboramadan et al. (2020); Tisu et al. (2020) shows that work engagement can be a significant mediating variable.

2.4. H4: Work engagement mediates the effect of leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior.

Ghosh et al. (2014) stated that the strength and weakness of a person's perception of justice in an organization can influence the quality of relationships between superiors and subordinates as well as the level of employee engagement in work and determine how employees will tend to behave well or not towards the organization. This is supported by research conducted by Montañez-Juan et al. (2019) which explains that organizational justice can be a moderating variable on the influence of work on job satisfaction. Other research conducted by Peprah (2020) shows that the organizational justice variable can moderate the influence of employee perceptions on employee engagement. Sarti (2019) in his research stated that the resulting moderating role is significant where a sense of justice can influence the quality of LMX relationships that occur and influence employees' sense of engagement with their work.

H5: Organizational justice moderates the effect of leader-member exchange on work engagement.

3. Methods

The population in this study were employees who worked in the Regional III National Road Implementation Work Unit, Bali Province. The total number of employees is 88 employees (including the head of the work unit). The population in this study was 87 employees (excluding the head of the work unit). This research uses a saturated sampling method using non-probability sampling. All employees are used as samples. Saturated sampling technique is a sampling technique where all members of the population are used as samples. There are 30 Civil Servants, 58 Non-PNS Employees (including PPPK and Honorary). The sample in this study was 87 employees, not including the head of the work unit because at that level no longer had a superior and, in that position, he could not assess himself regarding leader-member exchange, organizational justice, work engagement, and organizational citizenship behavior. A sample of 87 employees was used to find out how employees behave.

The method used to collect data in this research was a survey. A questionnaire is a data collection technique by distributing a list of written statements regarding the research object, where the questionnaire is distributed directly to employees of the Bali Province Region III National Road Implementation Work Unit. The questionnaire used consists of closed statements. The data analysis technique used is Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) or a variance-based

structural equation model or component-based SEM called Partial Least Square (PLS). SEM PLS analysis in the research was carried out using the Smart PLS software application.

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing aims to test the significance of the constants and independent variables contained in the equation individually, whether there is an influence on the value of the dependent variable. Hypothesis testing is carried out using the t-test, namely separating tests of direct influence and indirect influence or testing mediating and moderating variables. Hypothesis testing using PLS can be seen from the bootstrapping results in the t-statistic table to see whether there is an influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable with a significance level of 5%. A level of significance of 5 percent on an exogenous variable is considered to influence the endogenous variable if it has a t-statistic greater than 1.96 (Hair et al., 2021:94). The test results are presented in table 1.

Table 1 Path Coefficient Test Results

	Original Sampel (O)	Sampel Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Leader-member Exchange -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.730	0.719	0.062	11.764	0.000
Leader-member Exchange -> Work Engagement	0.264	0.234	0.123	2.141	0.035
Moderating Effect 1 -> Work Engagement	-0.130	-0.129	0.050	2.601	0.011
Work Engagement -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.239	0.258	0.077	3.119	0.002

Primary Data, 2024

The p-value of the leader-member exchange variable on organizational citizenship behavior is 0.000 < 0.05 with a beta value of 0.730 with a t statistical value of 11.764 compared to the t-table of 1.96. The t-statistic value > t-table (11.764 > 1.96) means it can be concluded that leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the first hypothesis (H1) which states that leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior is accepted.

The p-value of the leader-member exchange variable on work engagement is 0.035 < 0.05 with a beta value of 0.264 with a t statistic value of 2.141 compared to the t-table of 1.96. The t-statistic value > t-table (2.141 > 1.96) means it can be concluded that leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on work engagement. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the second hypothesis (H2) which states that leader-member exchange has a positive and significant effect on work engagement is accepted.

The p-value of the leader-member exchange variable on work engagement with organizational justice as a moderator is 0.011 < 0.05 with a t statistical value of 2.601 compared to the t-table of 1.96. At a significance level of 5 percent, organizational justice moderates the effect of leader-member exchange on work engagement. The t-statistic value > t-table (2.601 > 1.96), it can be concluded that organizational justice is able to moderate the effect of leader-member exchange on work engagement.

The p-value of the work engagement variable on organizational citizenship behavior is 0.002 < 0.05 with a beta value of 0.239 with a t statistic value of 3.119 compared to the t-table of 1.96. The t-statistic value > t-table (3.119 > 1.96) means it can be concluded that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior. Based on the results of the hypothesis test, the third hypothesis (H3) which states that work engagement has a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior is accepted.

Table 2 Indirect Effect Test Results

	Original Sampel (O)	Sampel Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Leader-member Exchange -> Work Engagement -> Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.063	0.057	0.031	2.013	0.047

Primary Data, 2024

The p-value of the leader-member exchange variable on organizational citizenship behavior with work engagement as a mediator is $0.047 < 0.05$ with a beta value of 0.063 with a t statistic value of 2.013 compared to the t-table of 1.96. The t-statistic value $>$ t-table ($2.013 > 1.96$) means it can be concluded that work engagement is able to mediate the influence of leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the fourth hypothesis (H4) which states that work engagement mediates the influence of leader-members on organizational citizenship behavior is accepted. The basis for testing the type of mediation can be determined by examining the significance of the direct effect between variables, using the approach of Hair et al. (2021:142) is presented in figure 1.

Figure 1 Testing the Effect of Mediation

Information:

- P1: effect of X on M
- P2: effect of M on Y
- P3: effect of X on Y

Leader-member exchange on work engagement (P1) has a positive and significant effect (path coefficient 0.264 and p-value of 0.035).

Work engagement on organizational citizenship behavior (P2) has a positive and significant effect (path coefficient 0.239 and p-value of 0.002).

Leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior (P3) has a positive and significant effect (path coefficient 0.730 and p-value of 0.000).

The mediating role of work engagement on the influence of leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior, based on the results of examining the effects of indirect influences, investigation of the three influences (a, b, and c) shows that p1, p2 and p3 are positive and significant, so the type of mediating variable in The model is complementary partial mediation. These results indicate that work engagement partially mediates and complements the effect of leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior. The research results show that the higher

the quality of the leader-member exchange, the higher the work engagement felt by employees, which results in increased employee organizational citizenship behavior.

4.2. Moderation Effect

Table 3 Moderation Effect Test Results

Variable	Path coefficients (Original Sampel/O)	Sam ple Mea n	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	p-value
Organizational justice moderates the leader-member exchange relationship on work engagement	-0.130	- 0.129	0.050	2.601	0.011

Primary Data, 2024

Based on table 3 above, through the moderation procedure (Solimun, 2020:36), the p-value of the moderating effect of organizational justice on the influence of leader-member exchange on work engagement is 0.011. The results show that organizational justice moderates significantly. The p-value < 0.05 ($0.011 < 0.05$) with a beta value of negative (-) 0.130, it can be concluded that organizational justice moderates and weakens the influence of leader-member exchange on work engagement. The p-value of 0.011 indicates that there is a significant moderating effect. These results also indicate that moderating effect 1 is a quasi-moderation as seen from the significant influence of moderating effect 1 and the significant influence of the organizational justice variable on work engagement with a p-value of $0.000 < 0.050$ which indicates it has a significant influence. These results indicate that organizational justice moderates the influence of leader-member exchange on work engagement. Based on these results, it can be concluded that this moderation role falls into the category of quasi moderation. Based on the results of hypothesis testing, the fifth hypothesis (H5) which states that organizational justice moderates the effect of leader-member exchange on work engagement is accepted.

5. Conclusion

leader-member exchange and work engagement have an influence on organizational citizenship behavior. Leader-member exchange has an influence on work engagement. Work engagement can mediate the influence of leader-member exchange on organizational citizenship behavior and organizational justice can moderate the influence of leader-member exchange on work engagement. Theoretically, this research also contributes to exchange theory, namely the reciprocal relationship between individuals and individuals and individuals and organizations.

Social exchange theory explains that a person's behavior towards an organization is based on the exchange of benefits obtained and a person's behavior depends on the reactions and support they receive from the organization. Employees will contribute more to the progress and sustainability of the agency and provide a positive role that benefits the organization in the form of organizational citizenship behavior and work engagement in the form of employees feeling meaning, pride, dedication and energy in their work when there is an exchange of benefits because employees have the quality of leader-member exchange such as good quality close relationships, a pleasant nature and gaining the trust of superiors which makes them have an obligation to reciprocate the superior's treatment.

Employees have work engagement in the form of feeling proud of the work they do and assessing their work as meaningful, having energy, and being dedicated to their work will create a sense of loyalty which is demonstrated by showing organizational citizenship behavior by contributing more to the progress and sustainability of the agency, helping fellow colleagues. and maintain relationships between employees. When employees have a sense of justice in the company, they will exchange benefits by having a quality relationship with their superiors and will reciprocate the treatment of that relationship with work engagement.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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